

Smart Contactless Door Lock

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of
Bachelor Of Science In Computer Science / Software Engineering

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01

Introduction

INTRODUCTION

- Provide security to organizations.
- Access allowed only to authorized personnel with a valid RFID tag.
- Designed using 8051 micro controller and RFC522 RFID module.
- Output controlled via DC relay.

02

Problem Statement

UNDERSTANDING THE PROBLEM

- Lower Security
- Not User Friendly
- No/Low Visibility in dark
- Preventing the Spread Covid-19
- Key Duplication / Breakable

03

Working

RFID:

RFID (radio frequency identification)

- A tag
- A reader

Radio Frequency used

- 125KHZ

Read Range

- 3cm

Valid Tag in Range

- Indicated by buzzer and LED

Project Flow Chart

Project Block Diagram

Components

LED (Red),(Green), Buzzer

Solenoid Lock

LM2596 Module

Relay module

RFID Module

Arduino Uno

Demonstration

The image features a dark blue background with the word "Demonstration" centered in a large, white, sans-serif font. In the top right corner, there is a cluster of several small squares in white, cyan, and orange. In the bottom left corner, there are two small squares, one white and one cyan.

04

Scope & Future Work

Scope

- Automated system
- Affordable
- Accurate
- Multiple Keyless Entry Options

Future Work

- The camera can be used for facial detection.
- Can control it on remotely using ESP32.
- By integrating database we can store the log data.

Conclusion

- The integration of RFID has enhanced the security level in the door lock system. Tech And Modern
- Access allowed only to authorized personnel with a valid RFID tag and the door lock will open for a limited amount of time and after that relay will lock the door automatically.
- RFID based security is safer and quick answered when contrasted with the other framework like biometric or key lock.

The background is a dark blue gradient. It features several vertical white lines of varying lengths. Scattered throughout are small squares in three colors: light blue, light orange, and light pink. Some squares are solid, while others are hollow outlines. The overall aesthetic is modern and minimalist.

THANK YOU